

Gender STI

D5.3 – Communication and Dissemination Final Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following report will present the results of the Gender STI project's Communication and Dissemination activities carried out during the second period of the project, from month 19 to 36.

Overall, the project has been received with enthusiasm by the European and international science, technology, and innovation (STI) community, many of whom acknowledge the importance of promoting gender equality in international STI cooperation. The project opened new discussions towards gender equality implementation in bilateral and multilateral STI agreements, providing context and recommendations, bringing along perspectives from countries around the world and contributing to dialogues and international cooperation in STI.

The project's communication and dissemination activities have met all the expected KPIs for the second reporting period, exceeding them in many cases. In addition, engagement with the project's activities has also been high, producing collaborations with the European Commission itself and Gender STI's sister projects in gender equality.

These results have made us proud of the projects accomplishment during its lifetime and with high expectations towards its sustainability in the forthcoming years. We have no doubt that Gender STI has had a profound impact in the area of gender equality in STI dialogues and international cooperation.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report will discuss the implementation and results of the Gender STI Communication and Dissemination plan during the second period of the project. It will describe the key actions and activities carried out in communication as well as dissemination.

As a reference, the objectives for communication and dissemination are laid out below:

- Introduce the project to GENDER STI's target audiences;
- Create a deeper understanding of the GENDER STI project and its objectives;
- Promote GENDER STI and raise awareness about it;
- Transfer GENDER STI knowledge and outcomes to stakeholder groups that can use the information;
- Create synergies with other EU-funded projects and initiatives, in particular with SwafS projects; and
- Engage with key stakeholder groups to obtain feedback on project results.

Section 2 of the report will present the project's communication activities, including email campaigns, social media campaigns, and project events, among others. Communication activities aim to raise the project's profile as well as its results among stakeholder communities and foment gender equality in STI on an international level.

Section 3 will discuss Gender STI's dissemination activities, which are directly related to the project's results. Gender STI has been disseminating project results in different channels such as the website publications, scientific papers and abstracts, the European Observatory on Gender in STI, and the final conference, among others.

Section 4 will go through the project's online metrics and overall key performance indicators (KPIs). We will report on the traffic to the Gender STI website throughout the project lifetime, the amount of time people spent on the site, the geographic location of the visitors, and the most popular pages and posts, among other metrics. In addition, we will present a status update on the communication and dissemination KPIs.

Section 5 will present the conclusion.

2. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In accordance with the project's Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1), during this second reporting period we maintained our efforts on communication activities increasing the projects awareness while at the same time sharing and promoting the project results. Through these communication activities, we ensured that the project became known to target audiences, formed links to sister projects, became known as a relevant voice in the STI field, and fomented a message of gender equality in STI.

Our communication activities consisted of the following: social media and web campaigns, email campaigns, attending third party events and hosting Gender STI events.

Overall, these communication activities established a solid base for Gender STI to transfer knowledge from its investigations. This base proved to be extremely useful when we disseminated the project's results to target audiences.

2.1 Campaigns

2.1.1 International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2023

Figure 1: Examples of Social Media Posts for IDWGS 2023

Gender STI launched a social media campaign on February 10 2023 during the week of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (IDWGS). The campaign shared one of the prototypes developed in the Gender STI Co-Design Labs titled "Building bridges from Girls to Women Leading Voices STI". Through this campaign, we aimed to introduce different problems and actions regarding women's

accomplishment of occupying the promising STI arena. The objective was to awaken women's careers in STI through international gender equality awareness.

The campaign was launched on Gender STI's social media channels (LinkedIn, and Twitter).

A summary of the campaign's results is provided below.

- **Total Organic Impressions Across All Channels:** 471 impressions (views) on LinkedIn + Twitter
- **Total Organic Engagements:** 45
- **LinkedIn Engagement Rate:** 8%
- **Twitter Engagement Rate:** 1,5%

(Engagements: This refers to the number of times people have interacted with the publication, and includes likes, shares, retweets and clicks, among others.

(Organic: This refers to views and interactions that have been generated without running paid campaigns. The entire campaign was organic).

2.1.2 #WOMENINSTI - International Women's Day 2023

Figure 2: Graphic for IWD 2023

The next campaign was for International Women's Day (IWD) on March 8, 2023. Considering that Gender STI is a research and innovation project on gender equality in STI, an area that has long been recognized as a male-dominated field, we decided to focus on this theme. Thus, our team asked our international partners to share some of their initiatives that promoted gender equality in STI and enhanced breaking barriers and biases through education, research and innovation activities and events. The campaign showcasing these initiatives was launched on Gender STI's social media channels (LinkedIn and Twitter) and on the project's website.

Figure 3: Examples of Social Media Posts for IWD 2023

Our team informed the European Commission of the planned activities as well as the consortium's partner institutions and the nominees' institutions. All entities contacted promoted the project and the #WOMENINSTI campaign, which resulted in a far-reaching and impactful action.

A breakdown of the campaign's results is provided below:

- **Total Organic Views Across All Channels:** 690 views on LinkedIn, Twitter + Gender STI Website
- **Total Organic Engagements:** 110
- **LinkedIn Engagement Rate:** 22.8%
- **Twitter Engagement Rate:** 1,2%

(Engagements: This refers to the number of times people have interacted with the publication, and includes likes, shares, retweets and clicks, among others.

(Organic: This refers to views and interactions that have been generated without running paid campaigns).

In total, we featured 5 initiatives from the project's consortium partners for IWD 2023 campaign on "Breaking Barriers and Advancing Women in Science and Technology" that promoted gender equality in the field of STI. These initiatives are promoted by universities, corporations, and other institutions, representing 5 different countries (Argentina, Austria, Canada, France and Finland) (annex 1).

Figure 4: Final Blog Post for IWD 2023

2.2 Events

GENDER STI has organized and attended events related to gender equality as a way to promote the project and increase engagement with key stakeholders in the field of STI, across Europe and third countries.

2.2.1 Second series of Co-Design Labs

Following the first series of Co-Design Labs held in 2021, we organized the second series of Co-design Labs in October-November 2022. We were thrilled to welcome experts, researchers, company representatives, funding agencies, consulting companies, and universities to the Co-design Labs. These workshops focused on three forefront challenges facing women in STI: gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making, and the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

To facilitate the participation of experts from different time zones, two series Labs were implemented: the America & Europe Labs and the Asia, Africa & Europe Labs, hosting three sessions each. The Labs addressed different thematic areas for each challenge and co-designed a number of prototypes.

1. Gender equality in scientific careers themes:
 - Gaining women in STI
 - Retaining women in STI
2. Gender balance in decision making bodies and positions themes:
 - Supporting women in decision making
 - Inspiring women in STI
3. Integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content themes:
 - Enhancing inclusive knowledge production cultures in STI
 - Enhancing capabilities for inclusive knowledge production

Communication Actions to Promote the Co-design Labs

Gender STI carried out a series of online communication actions to promote the Co-design Labs, which was invitation-only. Because of this, the actions were highly targeted to increase the RSVPs and attendance to the event, and included initiatives on the project's website, email, and the third-party event management platform Eventbrite.

The project's communication activities proved successful, attracting a diverse group of participants from various sectors and four continents.

Invitation

Project partners sent out personalised invitations via email to key stakeholders working on gender equality across a variety of sectors, including government, science, technology, funding agencies, the private sector, and NGOs, among others. The Gender STI design team created a special graphic for this purpose, included below, which aimed to convey a message of problem-solving gender equality issues worldwide.

Figure 5: Invitation for the Gender STI Co-Design Lab

Eventbrite

When considering the promotion of the Co-design Labs, the project communication team decided to use Eventbrite as the main event landing page to reduce the number of steps participants had to take in order to register.

Eventbrite served as the main landing page for the Co-design Lab and was included in all the personal invitations sent by the project consortium. It provided a short and compelling event description, which you can see below, and allowed interested participants to register for the Co-design Labs in less than five minutes. Participants received their tickets to the event via email and different reminders scheduled on an email campaign launched through MailChimp about the event one day and one hour before it started, which included a guide for participants, the link to connect, and the agenda.

Figure 6: Lab registration landing page on Eventbrite

Full Eventbrite Description

"The Gender STI project will host a series of co-design lab workshops to address three of the forefront challenges facing women in science, technology and innovation (STI): gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions and the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

Adopting an intersectional approach to gender, we will address inclusiveness and diversity as guiding principles to integrate the gender perspective in STI dialogues. Gender STI is an international project, and as such will host two series of Labs to accommodate participants from Europe, America, Africa, and Asia.

The series of three facilitated interactive Labs, aims to identify the key issues in these areas and develop potential solutions using design thinking and online facilitated processes. The Co-design Labs will take place online over a period of three separate days in October and November 2022. Each workshop will last approximately three hours and will include about 30 participants. As spaces are limited, we ask that you please make sure you will be available to attend all three Lab days.

Prior to the Labs, participants will each be assigned a specific challenge and receive a guide with background information as a reference for the discussion. They will then work with members of the Gender STI consortium during the event and share their knowledge and experiences related to specific challenges; discuss opportunities in their country or institution to tackle them; and co-design potential solutions that can be implemented to foment greater equality in these areas in the weeks, months and years ahead.

Input from participants in each challenge will contribute to a roadmap with recommendations that will be presented to the European Commission and shared with other decision-makers from countries interested in gender equality. All

participants will be included as contributors to this roadmap, which will also be featured in the project's European Observatory on Gender in STI. In addition, participants will be invited to form part of Gender STI's Community of Practice, a group of leaders that work to foster gender equality in STI in their home countries and institutions.

We hope you can join us on this important endeavour and help us make a true difference for women in STI from all over the world."

Blog actions

We used the Gender STI website to post the America & Europe Lab agenda for the Co-Design Labs, informing interested participants of the key elements of the online Lab sessions. It should be noted that to announce the Labs, we did not use our social media channels to promote the Co-Design Labs because the online event was invitation-only and designed for an intensive online interactive activity for a limited number of participants. After the labs, we also published a blog post providing the audience with the session's insights and methodology (see annex 2 and 3).

Social media

As part of the promotion, we also used the project's Twitter, and LinkedIn accounts to communicate the latest updates on the different lab sessions. For each, we published a post with the activities undertaken, general remarks, and the next steps to follow.

2.2.2 Workshop on Prioritizing Recommendations

To ensure a thorough prioritization of recommendations, a collaborative activity took the form of a 2.5-hour online workshop held on June 9th, 2023, engaging 22 experts from around the world to establish prioritization and refine recommendations where necessary. Following this comprehensive process, a total of 17 recommendations were distilled, which form the core of the action plan. Each recommendation is accompanied by concrete actions for implementation, stakeholders required to be involved, and a proposed timeline.

Invitations were sent to a pool of more than 25 international experts, hailing from beyond the confines of the Gender STI consortium. In total, 22 prominent experts, including experts outside the consortium participated in the workshop. Guided by the facilitation expertise of FUTOUR, participants were thoughtfully divided into three distinct working groups, with each group aligned to address a specific challenge. These working groups shouldered the collective responsibility of prioritizing recommendations pertinent to their designated challenge.

Aligned with the findings of the previous activities of the Gender STI Project, in particular the outputs and insights gathered through Co-design Labs and expert opinion workshops, the project developed a set of recommendations to foster gender equality within formal bilateral and multilateral agreements, STI implementation activities, and the dissemination of international STI dialogues and cooperation efforts.

The workshop was promoted on Gender STI's social media.

Figure 7: Example of Social Media for Prioritizing Recommendations Workshop

2.2.3 *Third party events*

Events attended by GENDER STI partners during the reporting period:

- Strategies to reduce gender gaps in the digital society (Virtual), 27 April 2022.
- ICGR, 5th International Conference on Gender Research. Aveiro, Portugal. 28-29 April 2022.
- Next generation MSCA Conference: opening a new era for change. Université PSL (Paris Sciences & Lettres). Paris, France, 24 May 2022.
- COGS (Canadian Organization for Gender and Sex Research) 2nd International Meeting. Canada, 29-31, May 2022.
- EU-SPRI 2022 Conference: Challenging Science and Innovation Policy. Utrecht University, Netherlands. 1 June 2022.
- IEEE WINTECHCON2022 – “Smarter technologies for a sustainable and hyper-connected world”, Bangalore, India. June 2-3, 2022.
- GEARING Roles Project, “Roundtable: Gender equality mandates for high-level leaders”, (Virtual) 14 June 2022.
- Seminar - Women in STEM - Addressing the Gender Imbalance. The UK Science & Innovation Network of the British Embassy Paris. 20 June 2022.
- IUPESM 2022 - World Congress on Medical Physics and Biomedical Engineering. 12-17 June 2022.
- 4th Summit on Gender Equality in Computing. Workshop: "Act Together" - The Role of H2020 Projects and EU Initiatives & their Impact on Gender Equality". Aristotle University Research Dissemination Center Thessaloniki, Greece, 16 June 2022.

- R&I peers Workshop: "Gender balance for Innovation: Gender Equality policies and actions: Lessons. Impact. Sustainability" (Virtual), 12 July 2022.
- EU-Latin America and the Caribbean Forum: Partners in Change (Virtual), 13 July 2022.
- The 26th International Conference on Science, Technology, and Innovation Indicators, STI 2022., (Virtual) 7-9 August 2022.
- IEE BHI-BSN 2022. International Conference on Biomedical and Health Informatics. Ioannina, Greece, September 27-30, 2022.
- Workshop on Gender Dimension in Research. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Virtual), 5 October 2022.
- GENDER-NET Plus Final Dissemination Conference. Paris, France. 13-14 November 2022.
- GENDER-NET Plus Workshop - Integrating Gender Analysis into Research. Paris, France. 16-17 November 2022.
- ICCE 2022: 30th International Conference on Computers in Education. Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. 28 November-2 December 2022.
- Diversity at the Center of Research, Guest Speaker, Presentation of the Gender STI Project for interested students or members of TU Graz. Lecture Series, 22 March 2023.
- Workshop on gender equality and inclusiveness multilateral dialogue on principles and values in international research & innovation cooperation. Co-Organized by the EU Commission (Virtual), 4th April 2023.
- ICGR, 6th International Conference on Gender Research. (Virtual). Londonderry, Northern Ireland. 20-21. April 2023
- EuSPRI2023 Annual Conference. University of Sussex Business School, United Kingdom. 14-16 June 2023.
- RESISTIRE final conference (Virtual). Towards Inclusive Crisis Responses, 20-21 June 2023.
- ICWIP2023 - 8th IUPAP International Conference on Women in Physics (Virtual), 10-14 July 2023.
- Panel "Alianzas y Compromisos Multisectoriales: Democracia, Conocimiento, Igualdad de Género y Transiciones Justas" (Virtual), Fundación EU-LAC, 14 July 2023.
- IEEE EMBC Sidney 2023 - 45th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society. Sydney, Australia. 24-27 July 2023.
- Next Generation Innovators Summit. Madrid, Spain. 10 October 2023.
- BHI 2023 - The IEEE-EMBS International Conference on Biomedical and Health Informatics. Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA. 15-18 October 2023.

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

We have disseminated the project results, which form a toolkit for dialogues and international cooperation in STI, through several channels, presenting them directly at events and the final conference, publishing them on a dedicated section of our website and through the European Observatory on Gender in STI, and transferring them to stakeholders in STI via email campaigns and social media.

3.1 *Gender STI Final Conference*

The Final Conference of the project titled "Breaking Barriers: Advancing Gender Equality in International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation" aimed to present the Gender STI policy recommendations action plan along with other relevant outcomes of the project, such as the mapping on gender equality in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements, and the European Observatory on Gender in STI.

The event gathered scientists, policymakers, entrepreneurs, and other stakeholders to discuss, share, and collaborate on strategies and solutions to promote gender equality in STI on an international level. Some of the specific objectives addressed were:

- To showcase the innovative outputs of Gender STI.
- To provide a platform for discussion, collaboration, and networking among participants from diverse backgrounds, sectors, and countries.
- To promote the European Observatory on Gender in STI.
- To foster international partnerships and collaborations that advance gender equality in STI.

The conference was split into a one-day event (hybrid) based in Madrid, and two (virtual) satellite events in the period after. Both agendas are attached to this document (see annex 4). The one-day event was held on 5th October 2023, at the UPM premises. It included a mix of keynote presentations, panel discussions/roundtables and networking sessions. This was designed to maximise interactions between all participants (both physical and virtual). The two satellite sessions each had a 1.5-hour duration and were implemented on 10th and 19th October 2023.

The activity was targeted to the following target groups:

- STI policymakers in the EU, MS, AC and third countries, including funding agencies, government bodies and institutions focused on gender equality in STI dialogues and international cooperation.
- Scientific and research community – SSH and STEM fields.
- NCP networks in the EU and in third country partners; Industry leaders and innovators; and
- NGOs, agencies, associations, visionary individuals, and organisations that advocate for higher R&I quality through gender equality.

In total 125 participants took part in the Final Conference, 50 participants at the on-site event for the one-day event, and 75 participated online, at the one-day event and satellite events.

One Day Conference (5th October 2023)

The Gender STI Project Coordinator, Maria Fernanda Cabrera from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid opened the event at 10 am with a welcome to all the participants. Maria Fernanda Cabrera, Douglas Thompson from SPI and Paolo

Martinez from FUTOUR provided an overview of the challenges, solutions and outcomes that were developed by the project team.

The Opening Ceremony was then rounded off with a keynote speech by Silvia Rueda Pascual, Directo of Women and Science Unit at the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation.

Figure 8: Participants opening session

The welcome session was followed by three keynote speeches:

- "International co-operation based on principles and values" - Martin Penny, from DG R&I's Global Approach and International Co-operation Directorate;
- "Inclusive Policies and Practices of Gender Equality in R&I" - Karen Salt, from UK Research & Innovation;
- "Gender in Science, Technology and Innovation: new frontiers in applying a gender lens" - Alice Abreu, from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro;

Yolanda Ursa (Gender STI Scientific Coordinator) from Inmark and Gabriela Ferreira (University of São Paulo) then presented on the results and achievements of Gender STI and gender equality in STI dialogues: the perspective of non-European countries.

Three round-table sessions were then organised to address scientific and political discussions, as a way of discussing topics related to gender and STI and also to discuss the results of the project and gather feedback.

Each roundtable lasted around 60 minutes with one moderator and three/four panel participants representing different organisations – from inside and outside the Gender STI consortium.

The first roundtable was moderated by Elisabeth Kohler, from the French National Centre for Scientific Research, on the topic of "Political strategies for gender equality

in STI dialogues". Participating in the panel were Surbhi Sharma (from the Interactive Technology Software and Media Association), Luciana Ayciriex (from Inmark), Ligia Amâncio (from the European Platform of Women Scientists) and Liisa Ketolainen (from HAUS - the Finnish Institute of Public Management Ltd).

The theme of the second roundtable was "Political strategies for gender equality in STI dialogues". It was moderated by Maria Fernanda Cabrera. The panel participants were Marlien Herselman (from the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research), Miguel González (from Tecnológico de Monterrey), Sarina Gursch (from Graz University of Technology), and Silvia Kochen (from RAGCYT - Argentine Network for Gender in Science and Technology).

The last roundtable was dedicated to the debate on "Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Research and Innovation". Jutta Treviranus (from OCAD University) was the moderator with the participation of the three panellists - May Wang (from Georgia Institute of Technology), Nina Rilla (from VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland) and Shirley Malcom (American Association for the Advancement of Science).

Figure 9: Participants third round table

Before the closing session, Jorge Molina-Martinez, from the European Research Executive Agency, gave a final presentation on "Concluding remarks on gender equality and STI dialogues".

Satellite Events (10th & 19th October 2023)

Two 90-minute satellite events were held on 10th and 19th October 2023 as part of the Final Conference.

Yolanda Ursa, from Inmark was the content leader for the first satellite event on "Intersectionality and Inclusion in International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation", Paolo Martinez, from FUTOUR was the moderator and Jutta Treviranus, from Ontario College of Art & Design University, Shirley Malcom, from American Association for the Advancement of Science and May Wang, from Georgia Institute of Technology were the speakers.

The second satellite event on the theme "The Legacy of GENDER STI - Gendered Content in International Research and Innovation" was moderated by Kaisa Lähteenmäki-Smith, from VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland. Douglas

Thompson, from Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação was the content leader and Riina Bhatia, from VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland, Hlne Molinier, from UN Women, Katja Toropainen, from Inklusiiv and Essi Laitinen, from VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland were the speakers.

The presentations of the events can be found [here](#).

3.2 Scientific papers

During the second period of the project, the consortium partners have submitted several abstracts and papers related to the project results to conferences and scientific journals:

- Sarina Gursch, **Coding Initiative Provides Different Approaches to Inspire Girls for Programming**. 30th International Conference on Computers in Education (ICCE), organized by the Asia-Pacific Society for Computers in Education last November 2022.
- Giovanna Sanchez Nieminen, Nina Rilla, Riina Bhatia, Maria Merisalo and Gabriela Ferreira (2022), **Moving away from traditional STI - how to improve gender equality and inclusivity in STI?** 26th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators, Granada, 7-9 September 2022.
- Riina Bhatia, Maria Merisalo, Nina Rilla and Tuisku Salonen (2022). **From persisting gender inequality to inclusion in research and innovation content: challenging the gender equality norm in the STI fields**. Extended abstract to Eu-SPRI 2022 conference, Utrecht, 1-3 June 2022.
- Sarina Gursch, Luciana Ayciriex, Yolanda Ursa, Stefan Kutschera, Wolfgang Slany, Janina Onuki and Gabriela Ferreira (2023). **Perspectives on Gender Mainstreaming in International Cooperation in STI: A Comparative Study**. International Conference on Gender Research - ICGR 2023, Conference proceedings, Ulster, UK, 20-21 April 2023.
- Riina Bhatia, Nina Rilla, Essi Laitinen, Gabriela Ferreira and Catarina Milhazes (2023). **Integration of gender in international science, technology and innovation (STI) collaboration: learning from international feminist policies**. Eu-SPRI Annual Conference extended abstract, Brighton, 14- 16 June 2023.
- Maria Fernanda Cabrera and Yolanda Ursa (2023). **Transformative Pathways: Advancing Global Collaboration for Gender Equality and Inclusivity in Research and Innovation**. BHI 2023 - The IEEE-EMBS International Conference on Biomedical and Health Informatics. Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA. 15-18 October 2023.

3.3 Publications

The project results in form of reports, presentations, abstracts and papers have been published on the website section titled "Publications". This page is routinely promoted on Gender STI's social media channels to foment interest in project results and direct traffic to the website. To this end, we published every Monday insights and infographics from the project deliverables as well as a follow Friday series where we recommend reports or twitter accounts that provide gender related content.

Figure 10: "Publications" Page on Gender STI Website

Figure 11: Examples of Social Media Posts for #FollowFriday Series

3.4 European Observatory on Gender in STI

Besides the tab publications, we also created a section on the project’s website devoted to the Observatory, which is also a channel for dissemination to showcase the project results. The Observatory consisted of the following four sections:

1. *Gender Equality in International STI Dialogues*: In this section we outline insights from the mapping of international agreements studied during the project as well as identified policies and trends established worldwide related to Gender in STI.

2. *Co-Design Labs & Gender Equality Solutions*: This section contains the methodology and prototypes description from the Co-Design Labs hosted by the project.
3. *Gender STI Community of Practice (CoP)*: The CoP gathers more than 200 members coming from different backgrounds spread worldwide. In this part of the website, we explain the goals, mission and the offered workspace for the CoP. We also provide a link and invitation to become a member of the CoP.
4. *Resources*: This section houses a wide range of reports, policy briefs, videos and infographics shared by stakeholders supporting gender mainstreaming in STI. Resources are split into five categories: Gender content in STI; gender equality in scientific careers; gender equality in R&I international cooperation; gender equality plans; and gender equality policies.

Figure 12: “European Observatory on Gender in STI” Page

Figure 13: Examples of Social Media Posts for #GenderSTIObservatory Series

3.5 *Email campaigns*

Importantly, Gender STI has directly transferred results to identified stakeholders in STI who are interested in gender equality. We have created a series of targeted email campaigns with our project results.

Campaigns have been sent to the users who subscribe to our newsletter on the website, the members of our Community of Practice, Advisory Board, EU Sister Projects, EU funding agencies, and third country funding and other state agencies. In total we have 1,049 subscribers to the mailing list. Examples of additional email campaigns can be found in annex 5.

4. ONLINE METRICS AND KPIS

A big part of Gender STI’s communication and dissemination plan is its website. The website is the project’s digital hub that explains its purpose, shares its activities, and hosts its project results, among many other things.

We’re thrilled to report that Gender STI’s website has followed the positive traffic and engagement metrics of the first reporting period. A breakdown of the data from Google Analytics is provided in the following section.

Figure 14: Gender STI Website Traffic Since Launch

Website traffic since its launch in January 2021 reached 15,000 users. Our focus has been to disseminate the project results by re directing traffic to the website through the promotion of dedicated sections like the Observatory and Publications tab, keeping successful metrics of traffic and engagement.

Figure 15: Traffic Breakdown by Source

The traffic breakdown by source has been very positive. It shows that the majority of the website’s visitors reach it via a direct pathway, i.e., they type in the website or go directly to the website. Organic (unpaid) search is also a good indicator because

it demonstrates that the project has successfully positioned the website according to SEO best practices. Organic (unpaid) social is an important factor as well, a reflection of the high engagement the project receives on social media. Through the channel referral we can also deduce that the project has acquired mentions via third party members.

Figure 16: Average Visitor Time Spent on Site

The average engagement time is the average amount of time a visitor spends on the website. During the second period of the project, we increased the average engagement time (from 32 to 39 seconds). Nevertheless, the time per session has not been the expected throughout the project. This can be explained because since most of our content consisted of downloadable files and it was not necessary for the user to remain on the website. On the other hand, the landing page contains the basic information for the user, thus, they didn't have to navigate throughout the whole website.

Figure 17: Most Popular Webpages

	Page title and screen name ▾ +	↓ Views -----	Users -----
		32,039 100% of total	15,171 100% of total
1	A research project on Gender Equality - Gender STI	13,176	10,043
2	What is Gender STI? - Gender STI	1,679	1,067
3	Publications - Gender STI	1,673	687
4	About Us - Gender STI	1,240	842
5	News & Events - Gender STI	1,139	469
6	European Observatory on Gender in STI - Gender STI	908	454
7	22 Lessons From Women Leaders for International Women's Day 2021	737	571
8	Explore Resources - Gender STI	687	115
9	Co-design Labs & Gender Equality Solutions - Gender STI	496	200
10	Gender STI Community of Practice - Gender STI	484	191

The most popular webpages visited on the Gender STI website reinforce our idea about the landing page. It's the most visited page, which can indicate that visitors are getting all of the information they seek from that page.

The fact that publications, news and events and the European Observatory on Gender in STI are in the top six is also important, as it indicates that our main approach of disseminating results as well as re directing traffic to the website has been effective.

Figure 18: Traffic Breakdown by Country

Country	↓ Users	New users
	15,171 100% of total	15,191 100% of total
1 United States	7,117	7,041
2 Spain	692	687
3 India	655	653
4 Canada	604	600
5 Brazil	497	495
6 New Zealand	455	455
7 Finland	357	353
8 Mexico	332	332
9 France	319	310
10 Austria	308	307

As Gender STI is an international project with participation from European and third countries, including countries in North America, South America, Asia, and Africa we are very proud of having this depicted on the country traffic breakdown results. High numbers of European, North and South American visitors demonstrate that we are reaching our target audiences. Special mention to the inclusion of India in the top three, as this was not the case in the first reporting period.

4.1 Communication Quantitative and Qualitative Indicators

In this section, we will detail the quantitative and qualitative indicators for communication and dissemination established in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D5.1).

Table 1: Update on Communication Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
Availability of GENDER STI website	Website online 24/7	Website is online 24/7 since M2.
Website visits	6.000 visits	15.0000 visits
Social media followers	700 (Twitter: 600 LinkedIn: 100)	1080 (Twitter: 400; LinkedIn: 680)
Project news articles on website	60 articles.	73 articles.
Third-Party events attended by project partners	At least 60 events.	55 events
Number of presentations about the project at third-party events	At least 20 presentations	23 presentations

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
Promotional actions carried out by partners on their online channels	At least 20 actions.	More than 20 actions
Newsletters	At least two each quarter.	9 newsletters sent
Participate in joint meetings of bi-regional dialogues between EU and third countries	At least one meeting for each region partner of the project (Latin America, Asia, Africa and North America).	Gender STI participated in the Gender Equality and Inclusiveness workshop held in April 2023, as part of the Multilateral Dialogue on Values and Principles for Research and Innovation (R&I) launched by the EC in July 2022. The event was attended by 80 participants from 39 countries and several European and international organisations.

Table 2: Update on Communication Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions on online channels and links to its digital materials.	Gender STI has established itself as a leading initiative in the gender equality space and is frequently mentioned by Sister Projects, partner institutions, the European Commission and funding agencies outside Europe (e.g. FAPEST, CIHR).
Proactive online community	Community that engages with the project's content and promotes it.	Gender STI CoP gathers more than 200 members that contributed to the Co-design Labs and to disseminate the project results.
Contributions to other actions	An increase in the project's contributions to other actions.	Gender STI has acted as a leader in inviting Sister Projects to participate in its initiatives. Similarly, it has also been invited to participate in and promote the initiatives of Sister Projects.

4.2 Dissemination Quantitative Indicators

Next, we will present the status on the dissemination quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Table 3: Update on Dissemination Quantitative Indicators

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
Number of attendees to Project Co-Design Labs	At least 150	+140 participants from 25 countries attended 4 series of Labs. The Labs were implemented over 12

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
		sessions with a duration of 36 hours online plus asynchronous participation in between.
Email campaigns with project results	At least four	More than 10
Number of citations of project results in online channels	At least 30	More than 20
Number of visits to project publications page	500	1,270
Number of visits to Observatory page	500	710
Publish papers on GENDER STI results in scientific journals	At least 5 abstracts or papers	11 abstracts and papers
Policy briefs on GENDER STI research findings and recommendations	2 (one in M18 and one in M36)	2 Policy briefs
Number of attendees to project final event	80-100	125 attendees (50 in person, 75 online)

Table 4: Update on Dissemination Qualitative Indicators

Indicator description	KPIs	Status
Mentions by other projects, initiatives or agencies	Positive mentions of project results on online channels and links to its digital materials.	Gender STI has been frequently mentioned by EU Sister Projects and other gender equality initiatives led by partners, including IDRC 'We Count Newsletter'. It has also been promoted by state-level funding agencies, including Brazil's FAPESP and Canada's CIHR.
Proactive online community	Scientific community that engages with project's results and adds to the conversation.	Gender STI CoP gathers more than 200 members, including high-level women scientists and prominent innovators are engaged with the project's gender equality message and promoted its results worldwide.
Contributions to other actions	An increase in the project's contributions, specifically project results, to other actions.	Gender STI contributes to policy dialogue in STI and is involved in the Multilateral Dialogue on Values and Principles for Research and Innovation.

5. CONCLUSION

Overall, Gender STI is in a solid position when it comes to communication and dissemination of the project results. The project has had a successful performance throughout its lifetime and become a reliable source of information and leadership in gender equality and international dialogues in STI. It has succeeded in establishing itself as a must-watch EU-funded project in STI and gender equality and had formed meaningful partnerships with other EU Sister Projects related to its research.

Thus, while Gender STI has been active continuously launching and participating in communication activities to promote the project, our focus during the second period of the project has been to disseminate the project results through different channels and formats.

The consortium members are highly engaged with the sustainability of the project results and have actively participated in third-party events to present the project results. They also have written scientific documents and papers about the project to share its research with the R&I community. The main insights collected from Gender STI research have been published via email, social media campaigns and website publications, as well as through the European Observatory on Gender in STI.

All in all, we believe that Gender STI has successfully established a groundwork on different topics which have not been explored in depth until now such as gender equality in dialogues and international cooperation in STI. The Gender STI consortium has demonstrated its high commitment to disseminate the project achievements and transfer knowledge to implement gender equality in STI, opening the scope to other areas at an international level, which we hope endures in the forthcoming years.

ANNEX 1 – BLOG FOR IWD 2023

Gender STI Partner Initiatives for International Women's Day 2023: Breaking Barriers and Advancing Women in Science and Technology

[NEWS](#)

08.02.2023

The International Women's Day celebrates and acknowledges women's achievements while reminding us of the work that still needs to be done to achieve gender equality. One area that has long been recognized as a male-dominated field is science, technology, and innovation (STI). In this regard, Gender STI international women's day 2023 campaign would like to showcase the initiatives of our consortium partners that promote gender equality in this field, trying to break barriers and biases through education, research, and innovation activities and events. Some outstanding actions are detailed below.

1. [TU Graz University Coding Week](#)

Austrian University of Technology (TU Graz) and their Office for Gender Equality & Equal Opportunity provide competencies in the field of Gender Mainstreaming and Diversity Management.

Their most recent initiative, coding week, aims to provide girls with a positive experience in programming. The project leaders had to overcome stereotypes about what girls are interested in, which can be challenging in technology. Despite this, they found that providing female trainers, and creating inclusive, diverse learning materials was a practical approach to engaging girls in programming, exemplifying how girls can be enhanced to pursue a career in STEM.

2. [VTT's Internal Diversity, Equality, and Inclusion \(DEI\) working group](#)

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd is a Finnish, wholly state-owned, and independent research institution that promotes the wide-ranging utilization and commercialization of research and technology in commerce and society.

As part of the centers' sustainability program in 2023, their focus was on diversity, equality, and inclusion. To promote this matter within VTT, they launched a working group that involves more than 20 participants and aims to train employees on DEI issues. One of the challenges that the VTT team has encountered is resistance to the

initiative, highlighting the need for ongoing work to promote the importance and benefits of DEI.

3. [RAGCyT's Neurosexism, breaking bias initiative](#)

Argentine Network for Gender, Science, and Technology (RAGCyT) strives to promote women's participation in developing science and technology at national and international levels.

The network focuses on breaking down negative stereotypes about women in science and technology by providing information barriers to women's participation in these fields. Through virtual seminars with specialists and research in neuroscience, RAGCyT members could translate their findings into scientific publications and develop mass dissemination material.

4. [CIHR's Diversity, Equality, and Inclusion training modules](#)

Canada's federal funding agency for health research, the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), fosters research excellence related to the influence of sex and gender on health in Canada and internationally.

Among their initiatives to promote gender equality in STI, CIHR provides training for researchers and team leaders in Diversity, Equality, and Inclusion (DEI). They aim to enhance researchers' capabilities on DEI issues so that work life and research content become more inclusive. To this end, the CIHR team developed manuals, and short online courses addressed to researchers.

CIHR team members pointed out that the main challenges when implementing this initiative were the need for more time, resources, and resistance. Enough resources and impetus need to be given to highlight the importance and benefits of DEI within the organization.

5. [CNRS "Let's talk about equality" Conference](#)

The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) is among the world's leading research and development institutions.

CNRS' Gender Equality Unit is organizing a conference on March 10th to present concrete actions promoting gender equality within the institution. Under the title, "Let's talk about equality: from institutional policies to concrete actions in laboratories," the event aims to provide visibility towards concrete measures and actions implemented at CNRS to bring about lasting structural change.

The first goal of this conference is to share examples of policy instruments and actions to tackle gendered inequalities in CNRS at different levels (national, regional, and laboratory). Several gender equality representatives will take part in roundtables to discuss their experiences and the actions they implement. The second goal is to co-construct with CNRS employees the next Gender Equality Plan (2024-2026).

These initiatives by Gender STI consortium partners demonstrate the importance of ongoing work to promote gender equality in STI. While progress has been made in recent years, much work still needs to be done. As we celebrate the International Women's Day 2023, let us also commit to doing our part in promoting gender equality in STI and beyond. Supporting and contributing towards initiatives that promote diversity and inclusion in the workplace, encourage girls and women to pursue STEM fields, and challenge negative stereotypes about women in science and technology. By working together, we can create a world where everyone can thrive, regardless of gender.

ANNEX 2 – BLOG FOR SECOND GENDER STI CO-DESIGN LABS 2022 I

GENDER STI Co-design LABs: America and Europe Agenda

[News](#)

06/07/22

Agenda

Gender STI Co-design LAB2: sessions for participants from America and Europe

Session 1: Monday 24th of October from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

Session 2: Wednesday 2nd of November from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

Session 3: Thursday 10th of November from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

The Co-Design Labs

Gender STI's Co-Design Labs, which will include participants from 16 countries across four continents, focus on three of the forefront challenges facing women in science, technology and innovation (STI): gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions and the integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

The Lab sessions aim to identify the key issues in these areas and develop potential solutions using design thinking and online facilitated processes. Participants will discuss opportunities in their country or institution; and co-design potential solutions that can be implemented to foment greater equality in these areas in the weeks, months and years ahead.

Input from participants will contribute to a roadmap with recommendations that will be presented to the European Commission and shared with other decision makers from different countries interested in gender equality. All participants will be included as contributors to this roadmap, which will also be featured in the project's European Observatory on Gender in STI.

Challenges to be Addressed

Challenge 1 – Gender equality in scientific careers at all levels: The challenge is to attract more women to the STI field. Gender equality is always in focus, but by creating an inclusive and diverse work environment, it is also possible to promote

women who experience more than one discrimination. However, it is not about changing women but rather about creating an environment in which everyone has the opportunity to contribute. It is time to do diverse research, to create technology for all to get the best results.

Theme: Gaining women in STI.

Main Questions:

- What needs to be done to ensure that young women choose STI as a career path by creating a diverse and inclusive work environment?
- What funding mechanisms support a diverse and inclusive research field to attract more women in the field of STI?
- What policy actions can be established to attract young women in STI?

Challenge 2 – Gender balance in decision-making bodies and positions: Few women are in leadership positions or involved in decision-making. In academic events and conferences, for example, women are significantly underrepresented compared to men as keynote or plenary speakers or as panellists. The source of this phenomenon is widespread and often unintended gender bias. In this regard, success stories from women can help to raise awareness and to amplify women's voices and role in the STI field. The low number of women in decision-making positions throughout the science and technology system is a waste of talent and capacity that countries' economies cannot afford.

Theme: Inspiring women in STI.

Main Questions:

- How can the vision of gender be incorporated into the definition of STI conference programs?
- What can be done to promote inclusive leadership skills and women success stories in STI events?
- What can institutions do to guarantee a space for young women to be mentored and learn collaboratively?

Challenge 3 – Integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content: One of key challenges of integrating the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) content is the lack of capabilities for taking on gender analysis and assessment. Moreover, gender understood from the intersectional perspective encourages researchers to think beyond binary gender positions and integrate inclusiveness as the guiding principle for enhancing gender dimension in R&I content. The ways in which R&I content is created also influences whether R&I is reflective of the gender dimension.

Theme: Enhancing capabilities for inclusive knowledge production.

Main questions:

- What can be done to enhance gender sensitization in research and innovation funding organizations in implementation and reviewing of research calls and funding programmes?
- How can research institutions and researchers be assisted to take on inclusive research design and inclusive knowledge production?
- What indicators need to be developed to reflect inclusive knowledge production?

Schedule of Session 1 – Monday 24th of October from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

Main Goal: Opening, meet and greet. Join the challenge group. Explore the challenges.

- Plenary introduction. Organizers will describe the Gender STI challenges and introduce the lab method and schedule.
- Meeting the groups. The participants break out into three challenge groups.
- Exploring challenges and opportunities. Deepen understanding and reframing the challenges.
- Plenary closing and next steps. Talk about what's expected in lab 2 on the next day.
- Asynchronous assignment: Explore the opportunities and generate the first ideas (over 1 week).

Schedule of Session 2 – Wednesday 2nd of November from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

Main goal: Deepen understanding on ideas and opportunities. Build initial prototypes. Revisit opportunities.

- Plenary opening and check-in. Introduce the aim of the day's session and schedule.
- Focused reflection. Feedback on the opportunities and new ideas.
- Build initial prototypes. Converge ideas to create initial prototypes emerging from the reflection on the challenges, ideas and opportunities.
- Feed forward instructions to work asynchronously in Basecamp and collaborative tools. Roadmapping the next 6 weeks, 6 months and 6 years.
- Plenary wrap-up of lab 2. Introduction to the next steps.
- Asynchronous assignment: Prototype improvement, building and testing. Thinking forward (over 1 week).

Schedule of Session 3 – Thursday 10th of November from 14:30 to 17:30 CET

Main goal: Roadmap finalization and presentation of proposals

- Plenary opening and check-in. Introduce the aim of the day's session and schedule.
- Alignment in groups to fine tune the presentations of the proposals. Groups that have worked asynchronously share briefly their findings and decide how to present them.
- Plenary presentation of the proposals in a roadmap. Proposals of prototypes are presented indicating a roadmap of activities.
- Challenge groups reflect and renew on what we have learned. Participants reflect on the prototypes and on the lessons learned.
- Plenary launch of the GO, NO-GO prototyping phase. Discuss the asynchronous prototype implementation.

– Concluding plenary. The ways forward to prototyping on location.

ANNEX 3 - BLOG FOR SECOND GENDER STI CO-DESIGN LABS 2022 II

The Gender STI Project hosts the second edition of the Co-Design Labs

[NEWS](#)

28.11.2022

During the past three weeks the Gender STI Project has been hosting their second edition of the Co-Design Labs, addressed to enhance the integration of the gender perspective in science, technology, and innovation (STI) through international dialogues. We were thrilled to welcome experts, researchers, company representatives, funding agencies, consulting companies, and universities to the co-design labs. These workshops which focused on three forefront challenges facing women in STI: gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making, and the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

The event included more than 60 participants coming from 18 countries across four continents. To facilitate the participation of experts from different time zones, two Labs were held: the America & Europe Lab and the Asia, Africa & Europe Lab, hosting three sessions each. The Labs addressed different thematic areas for each challenge and co-designed a number of prototypes.

The first session considered reframing each of the three challenges these being

Gender equality in scientific careers

Themes:

- Gaining women in STI
- Retaining women in STI

Gender balance in decision making bodies and positions

Themes:

- Supporting women in decision making
- Inspiring women in STI

Integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content

Themes:

- Enhancing inclusive knowledge production cultures in STI
- Enhancing capabilities for inclusive knowledge production

The purpose of this session was to brainstorm in each group the challenge context, why is this considered a threat, specific objectives, as well as to identify all possible areas that should be considered on the future prototype. Following this, the next session was devoted to build the initial prototypes which would lead to generate recommendations and insights for the future. Hence during session two, participants used the information already gathered towards the prototype design process through generating the first ideas, enhance a deeper understanding and revisit opportunities.

The co-creation process of the prototypes consisted of defining the challenge objectives, actors involved, beneficiaries, and outlining the roadmap towards the implementation of the prototype with activities in the short term (6 weeks), medium term (6 months) as well as its impact on society on the long term (6 years).

On the third and last session, once the prototypes designs were defined, the different prototype groups had the opportunity to test their feasibility by facing an inter-challenge consultation. The groups presented their prototypes and received feedback from other challenge participants, providing them their general thoughts, possible changes, and recommendations to enhance the prototypes performance.

ANNEX 4 – FINAL CONFERENCE AGENDA

 Final Conference Breaking Barriers: Advancing Gender Equality in International Science, Technology, and Innovation Cooperation	
5 th October 2023 - Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	
AGENDA	
Time (CET)	Session
9h30 to 10h00	Registration and Energizing coffee Welcome note
10h00 to 10h15	Maria F. Cabrera, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Gender STI project coordinator) Douglas Thompson, Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação Sílvia Rueda Pascual, Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación Paolo Martinez, FUTOUR
10h15 to 10h35	International Cooperation based on principles and values Martin Penny, Directorate for Global Approach & International Cooperation in DG R&I, European Commission
10h35 to 10h55	Inclusive Policies and Gender Equality Practices in R&I Karen Salt, UK Research & Innovation
10h55 to 11h15	Gender in Science Technology and Innovation: new frontiers in the application of a gender lens Alice Abreu, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro
11h15 to 11h40	Gender STI: advancing gender equality in STI dialogues Gender STI results and achievements. Yolanda Ursa, Inmark (Gender STI scientific coordinator) Gender equality in STI dialogues: the perspective of non-European countries. Gabriela Ferreira, University of São Paulo
11h40 to 12h40	Roundtable: Policy Strategies for Gender Equality in STI Dialogues Moderator: Elisabeth Kohler, French National Centre for Scientific Research Panellists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surbhi Sharma, Interactive Technology Software and Media Association • Luciana Ayciréx, Inmark • Ligia Amâncio, University Institute of Lisbon • Liisa Ketolainen, HAUS - Finnish Institute of Public Management Ltd.
12h40 to 14h00	Lunch break
14h00 to 15h00	Roundtable: Recommendations for implementing gender equality in STI Moderator: Maria F. Cabrera, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid Panellists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marlien Herselman, Council for Scientific and Industrial Research • Miguel González, Tecnológico de Monterrey • Sarina Gursch, Graz University of Technology • Silvia Kochen, RAGCYT - Argentine Network of Gender in Science and Technology
15h00 to 16h00	Roundtable: Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Research & Innovation Moderator: Jutta Treviranus, Ontario College of Art & Design University Panellists: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May Wang, Georgia Institute of Technology • Lidia Żakowska, Cracow University of Technology • Nina Rilla, VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland • Shirley Malcom, American Association for the Advancement of Science
16h00 to 16h15	Final remarks on gender equality and STI dialogues Jorge Molina-Martinez, European Research Executive Agency
from 16h15	Networking cocktail

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 872427.

Post-event satellite sessions10th October 2023 - Online

Time (CET)	Session
14h00 to 15h30	<p>Intersectionality and Inclusion in International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation</p> <p>Content Leader: Yolanda Ursa, Inmark (Gender STI scientific coordinator) Moderator: Paolo Martinez, FUTOUR Speakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jutta Treviranus, Ontario College of Art & Design University • Shirley Malcom, American Association for the Advancement of Science • May Wang, Georgia Institute of Technology

19th October 2023 - online

Time (CET)	Session
16h00 to 17h30	<p>The Legacy of GENDER STI - Gendered Content in International Research and Innovation</p> <p>Content Leader: Douglas Thompson, Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação Moderator: Giovanna Sanchez, VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland Speakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hélène Molinier, UN Women • Essi Laitinen, VTT - Technical Research Centre of Finland

María F. Cabrera, Project coordinator, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Dr. María Fernanda Cabrera is Telecommunication Engineer, with a PhD in Biomedical Engineering, working as Associate Professor of Bioengineering at the Telecommunication Engineering School. She is the Innovation Director of Life Supporting Technologies (LifeSTech) research group, and secretary of ACTIVAGE.ORG association. In addition to her role in teaching, she undertakes integral positions as a project coordinator and technical manager in various European and Spanish research-funded projects. Her contributions encompass acting as a project coordinator, technical lead, or quality manager in a portfolio of over 20 research initiatives supported by the European Commission. With a remarkable track record, she has led more than 60 European research projects as the Principal Investigator, underscoring her ability in orchestrating impactful research endeavors. Her field of expertise spans a broad spectrum of applications in the domains of the ICT applied to different sectors like digital health and social inclusion. This includes areas such as services personalization, human computer interaction, telemedicine, and enhancing digital accessibility. She stands as the author of an extensive body of work comprising over 100 scientific papers featured in both national and international journals. She is member of the editorial board of the IEEE Open Journal of Engineering in Medicine and Biology and cofounder of the Committee for Women Engineering activities of the IEEE BHI conference.

Douglas Thompson, Manager, Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação

Douglas Thompson is a Manager in the International Area at SPI, responsible for the development and implementation of SPI's international strategy. With strong knowledge and experience of implementing sector evaluations and studies, he has implemented analysis and R&DI support activities in many countries in the EU and globally, and worked in international research and innovation collaborations around the world.

Paolo Martinez, Gender STI Co-Design Labs coordinator, FUTOUR

Paolo Martinez is an IAF Certified™ Professional Facilitator (CPF) with over twenty years of experience in creativity and co-creation applied to research, innovation and technology. He was awarded with the Platinum Facilitation Impact Award in 2020 by the International Association of Facilitators. He is the founder of FUTOUR (www.futour.it), facilitating projects in over 30 countries involving more than 150.000 people from communities, private and public organisations through participatory techniques and futurisation methods. Paolo is active in research, writing and co-creation on innovation, participation, rapid-prototyping and creativity and is collaborating with universities and research centers. He is a founding member of the Future Center Alliance and a fellow of the Royal Society of Arts and New Club of Paris.

Martin Penny, Head of Unit, Internacional Cooperation, European Commission

Dr Martin Penny is a Head of Unit for International Cooperation in the Directorate General Research and Innovation (DG R&I) in the European Commission. His Unit covers the EU's international R&I relations with the Americas, the Pacific, Russia, and Central Asia, implementing the EU strategy for international cooperation: 'The Global Approach for R&I'. Previously Martin worked as a Head of Unit in the European Research Council Executive Agency. Between 2005 and 2014, Martin held a series of posts in DG R&I in international relations, programme design, and as the Director-General's political assistant. Prior to this he worked for the UK Research Councils, including five years as the Director of the Research Councils' Brussels Office. Martin has a PhD in synthetic organic chemistry (Bristol University), an MSc in science and society (Open University) and held postdoctoral research positions in biological and medicinal chemistry in the US, UK, and Belgium.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 872427.

Karen Salt, Deputy Director, R&I System Diversity and Security, UK Research & Innovation,

Dr. Karen Salt is an expert on governance, systems and transformative change. She is currently the Deputy Director of R&I System Diversity within UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), the UK's largest public funder of research and innovation. She drives UKRI's cross-organisational strategic thinking and policymaking on system diversity and Trusted Research and Innovation. She has led and managed interdisciplinary research centres, collaborative research teams and large research projects, including those focused on producing evidence-informed interventions and policies. A sought after thought-leader and speaker, Salt works closely with leaders across Government, academia, civil society and industry and contributes to numerous international initiatives focused on research security, inclusive policymaking and responsible innovation.

Alice Abreu, Professor Emerita, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro

Alice Abreu, Professor Emerita of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, is a PhD in Social Sciences from USP (1980), and M.Sc. in Sociology from the LSE (1971). She was a Full Professor of Sociology at the UFRJ for twenty-five years. Since early 2000 her career has been closely linked to science, technology, and innovation policy. More recently, Prof. Abreu was the Director of GenderInSITE (2015-2017) and is a member of the Gender Advisory Board of the UN CSTD. Prof. Abreu is an International Honorary Member of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences.

Yolanda Ursa, Gender STI Scientific Coordinator, INMARK

Yolanda Ursa is the Director of Innovation Management at INMARK. Yolanda has worked in Marketing Research and Strategic Consultancy throughout her career, and she is an expert in innovation management and international cooperation. Yolanda has an extensive experience as project manager and coordinator of research and innovation projects funded by the EC Framework Programmes. Her research areas cover a wide range of digital and emerging technologies, including Cybersecurity, Artificial Intelligence, IoT, Big Data, Digital gaming technologies, Energy Transition, Health and Wellbeing. Yolanda contributes significantly to the human factors of technological solutions, including gender analysis and intersectional bias.

She is actively involved in supporting policy dialogues between Europe and strategic partners countries, leading the H2020 project GENDER STI to promote the integration of the gender perspective in science, technology and innovation (STI) in bilateral and multilateral dialogues between Europe and third countries (Canada, the United States of America (US), Mexico, Brazil, Chile, Argentina, South Africa, India, South Korea

Gabriela Ferreira, Postdoctoral Fellow, University of São Paulo

Gabriela Ferreira holds a PhD in International Relations (USP/KCL) and works as a FAPESP postdoctoral fellow at DCP-USP. Her research extends to Caeni-USP, where she contributes actively to teaching extension courses focused on International Negotiations.

Currently, Gabriela is member of the Executive Committee at the Innovation and Science Diplomacy School of the University of São Paulo (InnSciD-USP). She's also a researcher for the Horizon 2020 GENDER STI project, emphasizing her commitment to addressing intersectional gender aspects within Science, Technology, and Innovation in the field of International Relations.

Her research interests cover areas as cultural, science and innovation diplomacy, with focus on intersectional gender dynamics in international dialogues on science, technology and innovation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 872427.

Elisabeth Kohler, Senior Policy Officer, French National Centre for Scientific Research

Elisabeth Kohler is the director of the Gender Equality Unit at the French national Centre for Scientific Research since 2018. She has a long experience in different fields, ranging gender equality plans to innovation policies, European project management and international cooperation. She is currently the coordinator of the EU project GENDER-NET Plus that is dealing with the integration of the gender dimension in research content. Prior to this, she worked as project manager for scientific infrastructures, as well as climate change and raw materials programmes. She holds a Master's degree in cultural history.

Surbhi Sharma, Founder, Interactive Technology Software and Media Association

Surbhi Sharma has been a serial entrepreneur since 1995. Alongside her business, in 2001 she initiated the organisation, Interactive Technology Software and Media Association (ITSMA). ITSMA, the non-profit organization, caters to the needs of SMEs in the International and domestic market. They assist international companies access the Indian market, for the right partnerships and collaborations. She has participated in many European Union funded projects and she is a partner of the Gender STI project. She is the coordinator of the National Contact Point of the ICT programme of FP7 and also the National Representative of the European Ideal-IST network. Surbhi is also active in the social sector, wherein she set up a Development organization, Anchorage to serve the under privileged women and children. She has had an early exposure to diverse development programs with both Indian and International groups such as Rotract Club, OPIRG (Ontario Public Interest Research Group) and McMaster University, Hamilton.

Surbhi has a Postgraduate degree in Computer Science and is invited to speak at conferences across the world each year.

Luciana Aycirix, Gender STI Senior Researcher, INMARK

Luciana Aycirix is a Senior Consultant at INMARK. She has more than 15 years of experience in managing international cooperation on Science, Technology and Innovation and interdisciplinary programmes and projects between the European Union and Latin America and the Caribbean. She worked with national and international authorities and institutions, promoting dialogue between main actors responsible for national Science and Technology policy.

She was in charge of the technical and financial management of more than 25 European Union-funded research and innovation projects. As a Project Manager at the Ministry of Science, Technology and Productive Innovation in Argentina. She also led the Political Dialogue on STI between Latin America, the Caribbean and the European Union and participated at the Senior Officials Meetings of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean and the European Union States in STI as well as in the bi regional Working Groups meetings.

Lígia Amâncio, Professor, University Institute of Lisbon

Lígia Amâncio graduated in Psychology and Education and holds a PhD in Sociology. She is emeritus professor at the University Institute of Lisbon (ISCTE-IUL). The publication of her PhD research in 1994 (Male and Female. The social construction of difference, 3rd edition in 2011) marked the development of gender studies in Portugal. Her research interests focus on the discrimination of women at work in high status professions such as science, politics, medicine, the judiciary. Among other research activities she integrated the team responsible for the first survey of the Portuguese scientific community (results published in 1995), participated in the Portuguese research team of the ISSP (International Social Survey program) surveys on Family and Gender in 2004 and 2014 and chaired the Portuguese team of the H2020 Coordination and Support Action SAGE (Systematic Action for Gender Equality, 2016-2019). She was also President of the Commission for Equality and Women's Rights (1996-1998) of the Portuguese government, member of the European Research Advisory Board (2001-2004) and Vice-President of the Foundation for Science and Technology of the Ministry of Science and Technology (2006-2012).

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Liisa Ketolainen, Specialist on Gender Equality, HAUS - Finnish Institute of Public Management

Liisa Ketolainen works as a specialist in gender equality and advises the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland on the global Generation Equality campaign. With multi-stakeholder cooperation and measurable goals, the UN Women convened Generation Equality is currently the biggest effort in enhancing gender equality globally. In the Generation Equality campaign, Finland is a co-leader of the Action Coalition on Technology and Innovations for Gender Equality, committed to bridging gender gaps in digital access and competences, investing in feminist technologies and innovation, building inclusive innovation ecosystems, as well as preventing and eliminating online and tech-facilitated gender-based violence and discrimination. Advocating the opportunities of technology and innovation for gender equality, Liisa wants to see both technology development as well as relevant public regulation, policies and programs be human rights-based with embedded accountability. Open University) and held postdoctoral research positions in biological and medicinal

Marlien Herselman, Chief researcher, Council for Scientific and Industrial Research South Africa

Prof. Marlien Herselman (F) is a Chief Researcher at the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) in Pretoria, South Africa. In this capacity, she is in the Technology Implementation Monitoring and Evaluation (TIME) research group in the Next Generation Enterprises and Institutions (NGEI) cluster, leading complex projects in the Innovation Ecosystems domain. She is affiliated with various universities as an adjunct/associate professor (UNISA, Rhodes, University of Stellenbosch, University of Pretoria, and Regenesys) where she does supervision and co-supervision at Masters and PhD level. She was also Chairperson and founder of the Living Labs Network in Southern Africa (LLISA) since 2009. She holds a PhD from the University of Pretoria, South Africa, and is a rated South African researcher. She has a h-index of 26 and delivered 45 Masters and 31 PhD students. Areas of expertise: Innovation ecosystems; Mobile/Digital Health; ICT4D; Educational Technology; Design Science Research Methodology

Miguel González, Associate Professor Researcher, Tecnológico de Monterrey

Miguel Gonzalez Mendoza holds a BSc in Electronics from Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico, MSc and PhD studies in Artificial Intelligence from the INSA in Toulouse, France, in 2004. He works as professor–researcher at the Tecnológico de Monterrey. He is an expert in Machine Learning, Data Management and Computer Vision applications, in which he has advised 14 PhD thesis and 30 Master's Thesis. Dr. Gonzalez Mendoza is the former President of the Mexican Society on Artificial Intelligence and currently he serves as AI Consultant. Author of more than 140 articles in JCR, congresses and book chapters. He has served as general chair in national and international AI congresses and workshops. Dr. González Mendoza worked in several Mexican and European Union research projects (as local chair). Member of the Mexican Researchers System, Level II. Regular Member of the Mexican Academy of Sciences, Regular Member of the Mexican Academy of Computing. Young Scientist at the World Economic Forum for New Champions.

Sarina Gursch, Project Assistant, Graz University of Technology

Sarina Gursch holds a master's in industrial mathematics. She currently works as a PhD student at the Institute of Software Technology at Graz University of Technology. The topic of her doctoral thesis is gender equality in technology. As an advocate for women in engineering, Gursch has authored several publications, particularly around methods to promote girls in programming and Equality for Women in STI. FFG project Code'n'Stitch, EU Project Gender STI, and the annual Girls Coding Week enrich her knowledge in this field.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 872427.

Silvia Kochen, Secretary, Argentine Network of Gender in Science and Technology

Silvia Kochen is the Secretary and founder of the Argentine Network of Gender in Science and Technology (RAGCyT) since 1995. She is a researcher at the National Council of Scientific and Technology Research (CONICET) and professor at the Faculty of Medical Sciences of the University of Buenos Aires and at the National University Arturo Jauretche (UNAJ). Furthermore, Silvia is the Founder and Director of the Unit of Studies in Neurosciences and Complex Systems (ENYS), member of the Advisory Council of the Ministry of Women and coordinator of the CONICET Medicinal Cannabis Program. She supervised 21 Ph.D. students and has 132 publications (h-index: 20 Scopus). Silvia is also Film Director with a PhD in Audio-Visual Arts with 3 Documentary Feature Films as director.

Jutta Treviranus, Director, Inclusive Design Research Centre

Jutta Treviranus is the Director of the Inclusive Design Research Centre (IDRC) and professor in the faculty of Design at OCAD University in Toronto (<http://idrc.ocadu.ca>). Jutta established the IDRC in 1993 as the nexus of a growing global community that proactively works to ensure that our digitally transformed and globally connected society is designed inclusively. Dr. Treviranus also founded an innovative graduate program in inclusive design at OCAD University. Jutta is credited with developing an inclusive design methodology that has been adopted by large enterprise companies such as Microsoft, as well as public sector organizations internationally. In 2022 Jutta was recognized for her work in AI by Women in AI with the AI for Good - DEI AI Leader of the Year award.

May Wang, Professor, Georgia Institute of Technology

Dr. May Dongmei Wang is Wallace H. Coulter Distinguished Faculty Fellow and full professor of Biomedical Engineering, Electrical and Computer Engineering, Computational Science and Engineering at Georgia Institute of Technology (GT) and Emory University (EU) in Atlanta, Georgia, USA. She is Director of Biomedical Big Data Initiative, Georgia Distinguished Cancer Scholar, Petit Institute Faculty Fellow, Kavli Fellow, AIMBE Fellow, IAMBE Fellow, IEEE Fellow, and Board of Directors of American Board of AI in Medicine. She has 20+ years academic professorship and ~4 years industrial research experience, focusing on Biomedical Big Data with AI-Driven Intelligent Reality (IR) for predictive, personalized, and precision health (pHealth). She published 300+ articles in referred journals and conference proceedings with more than 15,000 Google Scholar citations, and has delivered 300+ invited and keynote lectures. Dr. Wang received BEng from Tsinghua University China, and MS with PhD degrees from GT. Professor Wang is selected into 2023-2024 national Executive Leadership in Academic Technology, Engineering and Science (ELATES) Fellow program, and 2022-2023 GT President Leading Women program.

Nina Rilla, Senior Scientist, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland

Dr. Nina Rilla is a Senior Scientist in Ethics and Responsibility of Innovations at VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland. Nina has 20 years of experience in Science, technology and innovation (STI) research and development in national and international projects. Currently, she is interested in responsibility-driven change and social sustainability and works in projects related responsible research and innovation (RRI) in regional innovation context, gender equality and inclusiveness in green transition, and social economy in post-growth for example.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 872427.

Shirley Malcom, Senior Advisor to the CEO and Director, American Association for the Advancement of Science

Shirley Malcom is senior advisor and director of SEA Change at AAAS. In more than 40-years at AAAS she has worked to improve the quality and increase access to education and careers in STEM for all.

Dr. Malcom is a trustee of Caltech and regent of Morgan State University. She was a member of the National Science Board of the NSF and served on President Clinton's Committee of Advisors on S&T. Malcom, a native of Birmingham, Alabama, holds a PhD in ecology from Penn State, M.A. from UCLA and B.S. from the University of Washington. She is a fellow of the AAAS and American Academy of Arts and Sciences (where she is International Secretary). She was co-chair of the Gender Advisory Board of the UNCSTD and co-chair of Gender InSITE. In 2003, Malcom received the Public Welfare Medal of the National Academy of Sciences, the highest award given by the Academy.

Jorge Molina-Martinez, Project Adviser, European Research Executive Agency

Jorge is the Project Officer of Co-Change and a Project Adviser at the European Research Executive Agency (REA) of the European Commission, where he delivers specialised advice in project management and feedback to policy. He belongs to the REA Unit C4.1 "Reforming European Research & Innovation (ERA)", which implements the Horizon Europe's programme "Reforming and Enhancing the European Research and Innovation System", whose objective is to prioritise investments and reform in research, networking, collaborating, scientific data collection and transferring R&I results to the economy. Jorge manages a portfolio of nearly 30 Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects in the areas of European University Alliances, Science Education, Citizen Science, Gender, Responsible Research and Innovation, and Open Science. He also contributes to the Feedback-to-Policy and Communication strategy within the unit, in close cooperation with other REA services, the European Commission and key external stakeholders. Before joining REA, Jorge has been working for more than 15 years in capacity building and internationalisation of research & innovation and higher education, both for the public and private sectors, including broad expertise in project development, management, and evaluation.

ANNEX 5 – NEWSLETTER CAMPAIGNS FOR DISSEMINATION

Invitation to the Gender STI Community of Practice

YOU'RE INVITED!

GENDER STI CO-DESIGN LABS: Tackling Gender Equality in STI Worldwide

ONLINE

OCT 24 and 25
NOV 2, 3, 10 and 11

Gender STI+

Thank you for participating in the Co-Design Labs!

Hi <<First Name>>,

We wanted to thank you for taking the time and effort to participate in the second edition of the Gender STI's Co-Design Labs. Our team was honored to welcome participants from all around the world and diverse backgrounds, gathering multiple perspectives on gender equality in STI. Your input has helped us create new prototypes that will contribute to advancing gender equality, which we look forward to sharing with you soon.

On another note, we have officially kicked off the [collaborative workspace](#) for the Gender STI Community of Practice (CoP) activities. As a member of the CoP, we invite you to share your insights, ideas, news, events, best practices, and research results that you find most relevant to achieving gender equality in STI international cooperation.

Invitation to Second Edition Co-Design Labs

YOU'RE INVITED!

GENDER STI CO-DESIGN LABS: Tackling Gender Equality in STI Worldwide

ONLINE

SEP 13, 14, 15 and 16
OCT 5 and 7

Gender STI

Today is the day! See you at 9:00 a.m. CET.

Hi <<First Name>>,

We can't wait to meet you in the Gender STI Co-Design Labs today! Your participation will help contribute to more equality for women in science, technology and innovation. We are including the link to the event, at the button below.

Please sign on at 9:00 a.m. CET. Thank you so much for your commitment and participation.

July 2022 Newsletter

**Gender STI **

EUROPEAN OBSERVATORY ON GENDER IN STI

July 2022 Newsletter

Dear Gender STI Community,

It's been a busy time for the project! In this July Newsletter we would like to share some of the latest updates. This includes the introduction of the forthcoming Co-Design Labs; our most recent report on the overview of gender inequalities in STI agreements between EU and third countries, and the welcome to new members of The Gender STI Community of Practice. Keep reading to learn more about it!

July 2023

**Gender STI **
EUROPEAN OBSERVATORY ON GENDER IN STI

July 2023 Newsletter

Dear Gender STI Community,

It's been a busy time for the project! In this July Newsletter we would like to share some of the latest updates. This includes the introduction of the forthcoming Gender STI Final Project Conference; The Gender STI Observatory, and the past Gender STI Workshop. Keep reading to learn more about it!

Invitation to Gender STI Final Conference

Gender STI Final Conference
 Advancing Gender Equality in International STI Cooperation

OCTOBER 5, 2023
 Hybrid/Madrid

**Gender STI **

Dear Gender STI Community,

We are pleased to invite you to the Gender STI project final conference "**Breaking Barriers: Advancing Gender Equality In International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation**" that will be held in Madrid, Spain on 5th October 2023. This is a hybrid event, and you can also participate online.

The Gender STI conference will bring together policymakers, researchers, funding agencies, government bodies, and high-level expert panels on gender equality from Europe and international partner countries. It will showcase the innovative outputs of the Gender STI project and provide a platform for discussion and collaboration to advance gender equality in STI international cooperation. The program includes keynote presentations on international cooperation, inclusive policies, gender equality in STI, and panel discussions on three relevant topics:

Final Conference Details

Gender STI Final Conference
Advancing Gender Equality in International STI Cooperation

OCTOBER 5, 2023
Hybrid/Madrid

**Gender STI **

Dear Gender STI Community,

The Gender STI final conference "**Breaking Barriers: Advancing Gender Equality in International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation**" is around the corner. This hybrid event will showcase the innovative outputs of the project and discuss ways of collaboration to advance gender equality in STI international cooperation. Join the conference and connect with policymakers, researchers, funding agencies, government bodies, and high-level expert panels on gender equality from Europe and international partner countries.

When: October 5th

Where:

- On-site: Universidad Politecnica de Madrid, Spain. You can use [this map](#) to help you navigate your way to the venue.
- Online: You can access the conference through the [following link](#).

Agenda & Speakers

The [agenda](#) includes keynote presentations on international cooperation and gender equality in STI, and panel discussions on Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Research and Innovation, and policy strategies and recommendations to advance gender equality in STI dialogues.

Satellite Sessions

Gender STI Satellite Sessions

October 10th - 14:00 CET
Intersectionality and Inclusion in International STI Cooperation

October 19th - 16:00 CET
Gendered Content in International Research and Innovation

**Gender STI **

*Looking forward to seeing you
October 10th & 19th!*

Dear Gender STI Community,

As a wrap up to Gender STI Final Conference we are looking forward to welcoming you to the last two online satellite events we will be **hosting tomorrow, October 10th & next week, October 19th**. Please find the details and links to access below.

October 10th from 14:00 to 15:30 CET: "Intersectionality and Inclusion in International Science, Technology and Innovation Cooperation". Within the current political climate worldwide, this session aims to provide resourceful resilience, by coming up with solutions that can sustain and grow a global support community, leading to ultimate progress.

- Content Leader: Yolanda Ursa, Inmark (Gender STI scientific coordinator)
- Moderator: Paolo Martinez, FUTOUR
- Speakers: